

Authors' Response to Reviews of

Assessing the best hour to start the day: an appraisal of seasonal Daylight Saving Time

Authors: JM Martín-Olalla and Jorge Mira. Reviewers: Michael C. Antle (2) and Andrew N. Coogan (4)
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RC: Reviewers' Comment, AR: Authors' Response, Manuscript Text

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We thank the Reviewers and the Editorial Office for their comments to revision 1, and for the opportunity to submit a second revised version.

1. Summary of the changes in the second revised version

Changes in the second revised version are quite limited to issues suggested by reviewer 2 and 4. We have only included some minor edits, listed here:

- We add a new reference in section 1 after the British Sleep Society recently issued a position paper on Daylight Saving Time.
- We add a question mark to section 2 title.
- In section 2, second paragraph, after the Earth's axial tilt we add "along a meridian" in the sentence: "along a meridian sunrise times change with latitude".
- The caption in figure 3 now reads latitude and longitude for Italy and Finland in a more compact way.
- Due to a comment by reviewer 2 we reordered the sentences in the first paragraph of section 3.

2. Detailed responses to reviewers' comments

2.1. Responses to reviewer 2's comments

Reviewer's comment DOI 10.1098/RSOS.240727/V2/REVIEW1 Reviewer 2 is Michael C. Antle

We greatly appreciate reviewer 2's work and, specifically, their comprehensive comments on our manuscript. We also offer our apology for the minor issues they detected.

2.1.1 Major concerns

RC: *1. Figure 1 - The revised version is much better, however, some new problems have been introduced. The y axis of 1B should be “Sun height at 6:00AM” I believe. Also, it is not clear what the new thick blue line labeled “at 6:00” is meant to demonstrate.*

AR: Thank you very much for this remark. Figure 1b actually shows the sun height at several hours of the day. However, please note that the phrase “sun height at several hours of the day” is inappropriate for the label of an axis. The axis displays “sun height” and the legend attached to every displayed line annotates the corresponding hour of the day.

The phrase “sun height at several hours of the day” could be appropriate for a figure title, but we are not using this. Therefore, to clarify this point, we have amended the figure caption accordingly to stress this issue.

The thick blue line shows sun height at 06:00, which is wavy at 40° latitude, in contrast with the sun height at 06:00 and at the Equator, which is flat (zero angle throughout the year).

RC: *2. Figure 3 - the panel in the upper right has $SRW^=$ in the wrong location. $SRW^=$ is meant to depict the time of sunrise on double DST, which would be at 11:30 for Finland, not 7:30. The author’s SRW^- and $SRW^=$ should be to the right of SRW (link in the lower left panel) not the left of SRW. The sentence in the figure caption “Note that work activity in Italy is constrained from SRW to SSW in winter, while in Finland, the onset starts at $SRW^=$ and continues during a long twilight time.” probably needs adjusting, as the use of $SRW^=$ doesn’t seem accurate here, so the author’s meaning is not clear.*

AR: This is a confusion that often occurs when discussing clock regulations.

Please note, SRW is winter sunrise time, 09:30 in Finland.

SRW^- is one hour before SRW. Therefore 08:30 in Finland.

$SRW^=$ is two hours before SRW, and one hour before SRW^- . Or 07:30 in Finland.

All these time marks are referred to mean solar time, or standard time if you will.

Therefore, on the horizontal axis, SRW is right most. SRW^- follows to the left; and $SRW^=$ is left most. The figure is correct.

During DST SRW^- (08:30ST) is rendered as 09:30DST [we advance clocks one hour in spring].

During dDST $SRW^=$ (07:30ST) is rendered as 09:30dDST [we further advance clocks another whole hour during dDST]. Therefore, when dDST is set, $SRW^=$ occurs at the “same” hour of the day as SRW does when ST is set. However, it is still two hours *before*, since SRW now occurs at 11:30dDST.

We hope this will clarify our point.

On the second hand we have simplified the wording in the figure caption. The new version only notes work onset and sleep offset.

RC: *3. Page 9 line 26-27: it would be worth mentioning also that drivers may not be fully alert in the morning, having just awoken, whereas most driver are in the middle of their wake phase for the commute home later in the day and are therefore more alert.*

AR: Thank you very much. Indeed, that effect is most worthy to mention. It is included in the new version.

RC: *4. page 9 line 52-54: despite revision, the authors argument here still does not make sense. Since NYC has DST, people there are rising an hour earlier than people in Bogotá, despite having later sunrises due to their higher latitude (the time change occurs before the equinox). Their start times are not like those in Bogotá.*

AR: As in the comment 2, this comment is showing a misunderstanding that we now clarify.

Assuming a phase delay in NYC relative to Bogotá associated with the delay in SRW we have a wake-up time around 06:00UTC-05 (or 06:00EST) in Bogotá and around 07:20UTC-05 (or 07:20EST) in NYC during the winter season.

After the spring changing of the clock, and all else equal, the wake-up time moves in NYC to 06:20UTC-05, (now rendered as 07:20EDT), much alike and synchronous to the wake-up time in Bogotá, 06:00UTC-05.

Also note that the fact that transition comes in NYC before the equinox is discussed in the section “Setting transition dates”.

RC: *5. page 11, line 21-23: The author has fallen for the Absence of Evidence Fallacy here. Legislation can persist for many reasons. The fact that legislation has persisted cannot be used as evidence against the concept of misalignment. This section need revision or should be omitted.*

AR: In this target section (paragraph), we do not extract consequences from the persistence of the legislation—as reviewer 2 infers—. We quote our wording at the beginning of the paragraph:

Should the phase of the general population be “misaligned” during the summer season under seasonal DST, then the regulations would have not sustained in time *OR* [stress added] people would have acted by delaying their preset time schedules in summer to offset the “misalignment”.

We then list evidences and extract consequences *from the lack of adaptative responses by the citizens given the fact that the legislation has persisted*. Lack of response is a telling response.

We stick with the paragraph.

2.1.2 Minor edits

RC: *page 2 line 9: Instead of “failed to prevail” perhaps “have yet to be implemented”, since many governments have passed the legislation, but it hasn’t been initiated in those jurisdiction.*

AR: We were quoting facts dated 2018 and 2022. We preferred not to forecast what may eventually happen in the future. It is still our preference in this new revision.

RC: *page 2 line15-16 (and p3 line 10): “Primordial” is not a word used frequently by the English-speaking public. To make the message more accessible to the public, consider "original"*

AR: Noted. The word “primordial” has been replaced by “original” in the few occurrences of the word.

RC: *page 2 line 28: “vowing to put an end to the practice” overstates the position of the cited papers. “advocate to end the practice” would be more accurate and collegial.*

AR: Thank you very much for this comment. We concur and amended the manuscript accordingly.

RC: *page 2 line 33: “surfaced to politics” needs rephrasing. Perhaps “these points of view have caught the*

attention of politicians”.

AR: This is very much correct. The manuscript was amended accordingly. Thank you very much.

RC: *page 2 line 37 “current efforts by the circadian community try to educate people in the ‘correct’ choice” is not very collegial. Consider “current efforts by the circadian community try to educate people in the consequences of the choices.” adding “generally advocating for pStdTime” is you wish.*

AR: Our wording was intentional. We meant that the current efforts by the circadian community do not try to educate people in the consequences of every choice, but only on the consequences of alternating clocks and of permanent DST.

We have amended the manuscript in line with this suggestion and in line with our point of view.

RC: *Page 2 line 39 (and elsewhere): “stroke” The word stroke is problematic in this paper, and I’d recommend doing a “find/replace” search to replace all instances of its use. In this case, I believe the author means “the loss of an hour”, which would be more accessible to the English speaking public than “the stroke of an hour”. When discussing time, “stroke” can mean the moment when the clock reaches a time (e.g., “the bells started ringing at the stroke of midnight”. In a paper where medical implications are discussed “stroke” can also refer to a cerebrovascular accident (CVA). To avoid ambiguity, avoid the use of “stroke” throughout, unless discussing studies looking at CVAs, where Stroke is likely the more accessible term for the public.*

AR: Thank you very much for this illuminating comment. As a matter of fact the use of “stroke of one hour” or “stroke of an hour” came to us from the reading of a previous published work, that we cannot recall at this moment. Anyway, we fully understand the issue. In this new version “stroke” has been replaced when unrelated to heart or AMI stroke.

RC: *page 3 line 2 “it is also the basis of” is not accurate, since the “It” in this sentence would refer to the subject of the previous sentence (Solar noon). It is the dawn and dusk light that help synchronize the endogenous clock. This sentence should be rephrase, perhaps starting with “Th[e] solar day is also the basis ...”*

AR: We have followed this comment to remove any ambiguity that it might have generated.

RC: *page 3 line 8-9: delete “now”.*

AR: Done.

RC: *page 3 lines 11 and 19. Give the authors arguments, it is very important to make clear when they are talking about solar time vs clock time. For these sentences, “solar noon” would be better than just “noon”.*

AR: Thank you very much for this comment. To improve consistency we have added “solar” to every instance in which “noon” is called.

RC: *page 3 line 13-14: “The axial tilt gives rise to seasonal behaviour in living cycles[35–37] and to latitudinal clines in living cycles.” This is sentence needs rephrasing. It is not clear what is meant by “behaviour in living cycles” and “latitudinal clines in living cycles”. I’m not sure what point the author is making, and therefore can’t offer a suggestion.*

AR: Thank you very much for this comment. We have rephrased these sentences, hopefully for the best.

RC: *Page 3 line 39-40 “Office hours that are available in Bogota”. I understand the authors point here, but is*

“office hours” the right term? Few, if any, “offices” would be open at 6am (or even 7:26) in either location.

AR: “Office hours” was borrowed from Roenneberg et al. 2019 (Ref [12] in the reference list), see the quotation at the beginning of section 5. In this new version we use “working hours” instead. We understand the issue raised by reviewer 2.

RC: *Page 4 line 52-53: “Equinoctial” is likely not accessible to the general English-speaking public. Perhaps “relative to sunrise on the equinox”.*

Thank you very much. This has been amended according to this remark.

RC: *Page 4 line 57 Another use of “stroke” here. Suggest “four-step” instead.*

AR: Amended.

RC: *page 5 line 3-4 “Around the spring Equinox the sun rises at 06:00 irrespective of latitude” this should read “06:00 solar time”, since New York observes DST by the spring Equinox, yielding a sunrise at 7:00 EDT.*

AR: Yes, noted and amended. We seldom make use of clock hours in our manuscript. Nonetheless, removing any source of potential misunderstanding is always welcome.

RC: *Page 5 line 3-4 “the stressor that synchronizes”. is problematic. More precision might be better. Maybe “the late sunrises that lead to late awakenings in the winter”. Synchronization refers to something specific that I don’t think the author has demonstrated, nor do I think that they need to demonstrate this to make their point. Plus, the word Stressor is not synonymous with zeitgeber, which would be important for synchronization.*

AR: Thank you very much. On a second thought, our wording was indeed imprecise: the reader may understand that the “sunrise” ceases to exist. We have reworded the sentence in line with this suggestion.

RC: *page 5 line 31-32 “sun height climbs to 31° above the horizon at this hour of the day”. At what hour of the day?*

AR: At SRW. We have amended the manuscript to clarify this.

RC: *page 5 line 33-34 “The branches with unbroken stroke” Here is another use of the word “stroke”, plus it is really not clear what the author is trying to say here, I think something was lost in translation.*

AR: Thank you very much for this comment. We have amended the picture. We now show the sun height as a solid line in every case, and the effect of clock regulations are highlighted by a background yellow shade. We have amended the sentence noted by reviewer 2 accordingly.

RC: *page 5 line 37 “there” not “their”.*

AR: Done.

RC: *page 5 line 51 delete one of the two uses of “huge”*

AR: Done.

RC: *Page 6 line 52-53: “and only in connection with war times or crises” should be removed, or “only” should be replaced with “often”. Newfoundland in Canada used double DST in 1988, and they were neither at war nor in a crisis.*

AR: Thank you very much. We were unaware of what happened in Newfoundland during 1988. We amended the

manuscript accordingly.

RC: *page 6 line 55-56: delete “quite”.*

AR: Done.

RC: *page 7 line 5-6: Replace “on the last hand” with “finally”*

AR: Done.

RC: *page 7 line 15-16: “The morning up-rises and the evening and night shutdowns are easily perceived” I think something was lost in translation, as it is not clear what the author means here.*

We apologize for this inaccuracy. We amended this sentence, hopefully for the best.

RC: *Page 7 line 17 (and elsewhere, page 8 line 34) - The general English-speaking public will not understand the word “Ephemerides”. Explain this more simply for your audience.*

AR: Thank you very much for this note. We amended the text accordingly and removed the word.

RC: *page 7 line 30: another use of “stroke”, suggest “loss”.*

AR: We amended and reorganized the paragraph in this line.

RC: *page 7 line 34. “Schools, universities, appointments, can only start at 7am or at 8am”. Suggest something like “Schools, universities, and appointments occur during fixed hours” Schools, universities and appointments can star tat any time, but generally the start times are constant throughout the year.*

AR: This intended to mean “at whole hours”. We have amended the paragraph, hopefully for the best.

Interestingly reviewer 2 is noting here one side effect of clock regulations: schools, universities, and preset schedules are generally “constant” throughout the year *under clock regulations*. Without clock regulations some, if not many, preset schedules may have turned seasonal.

RC: *page 7 line 36: another use of “stroke”, suggest “loss”*

AR: Amended.

RC: *Page 9 line 11-12 “shrinking little by little” instead of “little by little shrinking”*

AR: Amended.

RC: *page 9 line 49: “which of the two preset start times in the case of the 1810 Spanish National Assembly —10:00 in winter, and 09:00 in summer— was artificial”, “wrong” or “misaligned with the sun clock”. This question is not logical, as neither is wrong, artificial or misaligned, as both options occur during regular working hours. Rephrase or omit.*

AR: Our question was rhetorical. We agree that neither is wrong, artificial or misaligned. However, literature on this topic sees DST as a misalignment, and therefore suggests that 09:00 in summer (instead of 10:00) is misaligned. We note that 09:00ST is rendered as 10:00DST during DST, and the start time looks “constant” throughout the year (see comment to page 7 line 34).

In this new version we put forward the answer to this question in line with this thoughts.

RC: *page 10 line 39: use time-specific terminology, so “before” rather than “ahead”*

AR: Thank you very much. We replaced “ahead” by “before” in a few occurrences throughout the manuscript.

RC: *page 11 line 8 “in” rather than “on”.*

AR: Noted.

RC: *page 11, line 24-25 - shouldn't this be “advance” rather than “delay”?*

AR: Indeed it is “delay”. All else equal, clock regulations enforce an advance of the phase of the human cycles. Specifically an advance of morning duties, say wake-up time: 07:00DST is one hour earlier than 07:00ST.

The primary response to this external stressor would be a delay of the wake-up time. Say from 07:00DST to 07:15DST, which is still 45 min earlier than 07:00ST. But this is seldom observed.

No delay in wake-up times during DST means no or few discomfort with the aims and goals of clock regulations.

A delay in wake-up times during DST would mean discomfort with the aims and goals of clock regulations.

An advance in wake-up times during DST would mean propensity to further advances of the clock.

RC: *Page 11, line 52 and page 12 line 29: The use of “downwind” and “upwind” are not correct here, I think something is lost in translation. I'm not even sure what the author intends with these words and therefore cannot offer a suggestion.*

AR: We thank you very much for this comment. We have dropped out these words. They added no relevant context.

RC: *page 11 line 33-34: “in the following minute” in a paper about time use, it is probably good to avoid sayings like this, as they could be confused as being literal. The sentence should work fine by just leaving this phrase out completely.*

AR: We agree with reviewer 2 and corrected this sentence.

RC: *page 13 line 24: replace the word “actor”. In the performing arts actor is a person who “pretends” to be someone else. More collegial suggestions could include: experts, scientists, or advocates.*

AR: We have replaced the word.

2.2. Responses to reviewer 4's comments

Reviewer's comment DOI: 10.1098/RSOS.240727/V2/REVIEW2 Reviewer 4 is Andrew N. Coogan

We greatly appreciate reviewer 4's comments and attitude towards our manuscript.

RC: *I thank the authors for the very comprehensive revision they have undertaken. I agree with the authors' main conclusion that the timing of human activity is shaped by many geophysical and psychosocial factors, such as photoperiod, dawn/dusk time, social/work schedule norms, and of course clock time and changes.*

AR: Thank you very much. We try to highlight the many confounding factors that are associated with this problem.

RC: *Regarding my earlier comments about social jetlag, I am pleased the authors have addressed these. I would note that the key concept of SJL is that sleep timing on work free days is indicative of the underlying phase of circadian entrainment for the entire week, and SJL is the manifestation of the difference between*

workdays sleep timing against the actual entrained circadian phase; DST may worsen this if the phase does not entrain by social/work schedules become relatively “later” as a result of the clock change. It is this discrepancy between work day sleep/wake timing and the internal circadian phase that is thought to cause the health related adverse outcomes related to SJL. If the circadian phase does not adjust to the DST transition (as per Kantermann et al 2007) then SJL would broadly be expected to increase at the population level. As such, SJL is not just a description of weekday/weekend differences in sleep timing, but is indicative of something potentially more important. I think this might be incorporated in section 4.

AR: Thank you very much for this comment. We have amended the wording related to the definition of SJL to incorporate the refinement suggested by reviewer 4. In this context, we now state that work days entrain to the social life (work schedules) while work free days entrain to the circadian clock. We hope that will suffice. In our previous submission we already linked SJL to health issues as per previous studies. This remains in the new submission.

RC: *My point about the 2018 EU survey is that it was a convenience sample of the general population and although the absolute numbers responding were high, the representativeness of the results to the general population cannot be assumed given the very low response rate and the high risk of non-responder bias. For example, responders to the survey could reflect disproportionately those who have particularly strong beliefs on the topic - eg. extremely early or late chronotypes. I think this nuance could easily be included in the manuscript.*

AR: Thank you very much for this comment. We are well aware of these concerns. We moved the call to the 2018 EU Public Consultation to the very end of the Conclusion section. We now just state that the EU Public Consultation might provide insight to our comment on SRW start times and DST.

References